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IMPROVEMENTS OF DATA REPLICATION ALGORITHMS IN DISTRIBUTED STORAGE SYSTEMS

ВДОСКОНАЛЕННЯ АЛГОРИТМІВ РЕПЛІКАЦІЇ ДАНИХ У РОЗПОДІЛЕНИХ СИСТЕМАХ ЗБЕРІГАННЯ

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Abstract. *Aim of the study.* The aim of this study is to develop and improve data replication algorithms for distributed storage systems, with a particular focus on environments that employ system sharding, where each shard operates as a replicated data system consisting of multiple processors. The research seeks to enhance data availability, reliability, and performance while ensuring consistency across distributed nodes.

Methodology. The proposed algorithm is designed for distributed data storage systems in which shards jointly process client requests and transactions and are capable of interacting with other shards to support inter-shard transactions. The algorithm employs distributed consensus mechanisms and coordination protocols to manage client requests, execute consensus procedures, and handle node failures. The decision to use this approach is motivated by its ability to prevent asynchronous data replication scenarios, in which multiple replicas exist but one or more of them cannot be updated or accessed by clients. The algorithm was tested using a dataset containing detailed information about an organization's employees, enabling the evaluation of replication behavior under realistic conditions.

Results. The testing process demonstrated that the proposed data replication algorithm can efficiently distribute and synchronize data across distributed nodes. The results indicate a significant increase in data access speed, a reduction in latency, and improved consistency among replicas. Additionally, the experimental findings highlight the importance of selecting appropriate replication mechanisms based on specific requirements and constraints of the distributed database environment, including data consistency, network latency, resource utilization, and fault tolerance.

Scientific novelty. The scientific novelty of this study lies in the improvement of data replication algorithms for sharded distributed storage systems through the integration of distributed consensus mechanisms that effectively mitigate the problem of asynchronous replication. The proposed approach enhances coordination between replicated shards and supports reliable transaction processing across distributed segments.

Practical impact. The practical significance of the study is associated with the application of the proposed replication algorithm in real-world distributed database systems. By replicating data across multiple nodes, organizations can reduce the risks related to single points of failure and improve overall system performance. The integration of advanced data replication techniques enables organizations to meet the growing demands for data availability, reliability, and performance in today's dynamic business environment.

Key words: data replication; distributed databases; fault tolerance; scalability; availability; latency; synchronization; consensus algorithms; partitioning; sharding.

Анотація. *Мета дослідження.* Метою дослідження є розробка та вдосконалення алгоритмів реплікації даних для розподілених систем зберігання, з особливим акцентом на середовища, у яких застосовується шардінг системи, де кожен шард функціонує як реплікована система даних, що складається з кількох процесорів. Дослідження спрямоване на підвищення доступності, надійності та продуктивності даних за умови забезпечення узгодженості між розподіленими вузлами.

Методологія. Запропонований алгоритм призначений для розподілених систем зберігання даних, у яких шарди спільно обробляють клієнтські запити та транзакції й здатні взаємодіяти з іншими шардами для підтримки міжшардових транзакцій. Алгоритм використовує механізми розподіленого консенсусу та протоколи координації для керування клієнтськими запитами, виконання процедур консенсусу та обробки відмов вузлів. Обґрунтування вибору цього підходу пов'язане з його здатністю запобігати сценаріям асинхронної реплікації даних,

за яких існує кілька реплік, проте одна або декілька з них не можуть бути оновлені чи доступні для клієнтів. Алгоритм було протестовано з використанням набору даних, що містив детальну інформацію про працівників організації, що дало змогу оцінити поведінку реплікації в умовах, наближених до реальних.

Результати. Процес тестування продемонстрував, що запропонований алгоритм реплікації даних здатний ефективно розподіляти та синхронізувати дані між розподіленими вузлами. Отримані результати свідчать про суттєве підвищення швидкості доступу до даних, зменшення затримок та покращення узгодженості між репліками. Крім того, експериментальні результати підкреслюють важливість вибору відповідних механізмів реплікації з урахуванням конкретних вимог і обмежень середовища розподіленої бази даних, зокрема узгодженості даних, мережевих затримок, використання ресурсів та відмовостійкості.

Наукова новизна. Наукова новизна дослідження полягає в удосконаленні алгоритмів реплікації даних для шардованих розподілених систем зберігання шляхом інтеграції механізмів розподіленого консенсусу, які ефективно мінімізують проблему асинхронної реплікації. Запропонований підхід підвищує рівень координації між реплікованими шардами та забезпечує надійну обробку транзакцій між розподіленими сегментами.

Практичне значення. Практичне значення дослідження пов'язане з можливістю застосування запропонованого алгоритму реплікації в реальних розподілених системах баз даних. Реплікація даних між кількома вузлами дає змогу організаціям зменшити ризики, пов'язані з єдиними точками відмови, та підвищити загальну продуктивність системи. Інтеграція сучасних методів реплікації даних дозволяє організаціям задовольняти зростаючі вимоги щодо доступності, надійності та продуктивності даних у сучасному динамічному бізнес-середовищі.

Ключові слова: реплікація даних; розподілені бази даних; відмовостійкість; масштабованість; доступність; затримка; синхронізація; алгоритми консенсусу; партиціонування; шардінг.

INTRODUCTION

Typically, a Distributed Storage System (DSS) refers to a set of shared, logically interconnected data geographically distributed across a computer network. Designing a distributed storage system is a complex task that must consider numerous factors, such as the queries used to access applications, integrity constraints defined at the database level, node and network configurations, application identification, and data access requirements. The distributed nature of the data introduces additional considerations beyond those of a centralized database, including data fragmentation, partitioning, replication, and the distribution of fragments and replicas across different sites.

Data replication, in turn, is the process of creating and distributing copies of target data and sequentially propagating changes made to the source data to the corresponding copies. This distribution ensures that data processing is performed locally. The replication process enhances system security and improves data operation speeds. Additionally, the application can continue functioning even if the local server fails, as other servers with replicated databases remain accessible. From the perspective of data replication, maintaining data consistency in the database is more challenging because updates to a fragment must propagate to all its copies. The decision to replicate a fragment depends on the balance between the number of database reads and writes for that fragment.

There are two approaches to controlling the data replication process: synchronous and asynchronous replication control. In synchronous replication, replicas are continuously synchronized. In this approach, a transaction can access any copy of a data item, confident that the data item has the same value as all other copies. Since it is physically impossible to change the value of all copies of a data item simultaneously to ensure consistent

representation, the replication control algorithm must hide the values of other copies that are not synchronized with it (e. g., by locking them) during the change process. In other words, no transaction can ever see different values for different copies of the same data item. In asynchronous replication, unlike synchronous replication, replicas are not continuously synchronized. Two or more copies of the same data item may sometimes have different values, and any transaction may see these different values.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In today's research landscape, numerous works are dedicated to the invention and analysis of methodologies for developing improved data replication algorithms in distributed storage systems.

In the study by B. Kumalakov, T. Bakibaev [1] presented an algorithm for colonial data replication in distributed storage systems. This algorithm involves distributing data copies across geographic locations to ensure access even in areas with poor Internet connectivity. The algorithm described in the paper proposes a colonial replication strategy using Paxos at the colony level and Raft at the primary replica level. Paxos is used for agreement and acceptance of updates within the colony, while Raft manages leader election and replication among primary replicas.

The research by W. Lin and others [2] focused on data replication in log-based distributed storage systems. The described algorithm involves recording updates in a log for preservation and application to the in-memory data structure. Periodically, a checkpoint is created on the disk, and updates reflected in the checkpoint can be truncated from the log. The system can choose to save one or more checkpoints. Logical replication reproduces the entire system state, while multilayer replication separates

file-level replication. A variant of logical replication called logical-V includes only primary in-memory state support. Log merging methods are used to efficiently handle multiple replica groups.

Additionally, noteworthy works include those by R. Liu, J. Zhou [3], H. Jia, M. Goldschmidt [4], S. Solat [5], Z. Gong, S. Wu, Y. Xu [6], C. Duan, R. Jiang, Y. Zhang, B. Wu, F. Li, Y. Duan [7], J. Peng, S. Zhou, X. Liu [8], M. Dieckmann, S. Beyvers, J. Hochmuth, A. Rehm, F. Förster, A. Goesmann [9], C. Yin, Zh. Xu, W. Li, T. Li, S. Yuan, Y. Liu [10], Y. Xu, Y. Wang, B. Wang, A. Khan [11], A. Tatarkanov, A. Lampezhev, D. Polezhaev, R. Tekeev [12], K. Krotov [13], F. Karamimirazizi, S. Jameii, A. Rahmani [14], F. Yang, Z. Ding, L. Jia, Y. Sun, Q. Zhu [15], R. Dugyani, Dr. Govardhan [16] and others.

SEPARATION OF PREVIOUSLY UNRESOLVED PARTS OF THE OVERALL PROBLEM

While replication improves data availability, fault tolerance, and performance, it also creates challenges related to maintaining data consistency. For this reason, there is a need to develop more efficient data replication algorithms in distributed storage systems. Despite the many scientific studies, the issue related to the methodology for developing improved data replication algorithms in distributed storage systems remains insufficiently explored and requires further investigation.

The research purpose. The aim of this work is to develop improved data replication algorithms in distributed storage systems.

Methods, object and subject of research. The **object of research** comprises distributed data storage systems that support replication and sharding, within which informational objects are represented as sets of equivalent replicas deployed across different network nodes. Such systems are characterized by the interaction between server and client processes, the necessity of processing requests in environments subject to potential node failures, network latency, and resource constraints, as well as the requirement to ensure data consistency, availability, and fault tolerance during the execution of distributed transactions.

The subject of research is data replication algorithms in distributed storage systems, including methods for maintaining replica consistency, mechanisms for achieving distributed consensus, approaches to synchronizing object states, and strategies for the optimal placement and migration of replicas across network nodes. Particular attention is paid to issues of asynchronous replication, load balancing, minimization of average request processing time, consideration of constraints on node capacity and the number of replicas, as well as the impact of network topology and request intensity on the efficiency of replication algorithms.

The research methods are based on a combination of theoretical and experimental approaches, including

methods of distributed algorithm analysis, distributed systems theory, and modeling. The study applies the state machine replication method with client request ordering based on logical clocks, formal methods for describing processes and node interactions, as well as optimization methods for determining a rational distribution of replicas subject to node resource constraints and allowable response time limits. To verify the effectiveness of the proposed algorithm, simulation modeling of a distributed system based on a weighted network graph is employed, along with analysis of message transmission delay matrices and experimental testing on a dataset reflecting real information flows within an organizational structure, followed by an evaluation of performance, consistency, and fault tolerance indicators.

MAIN MATERIAL

Each informational object corresponds to a single process that can perform operations on it. During data replication, a process that aims to access target data can obtain it from any replica, optimizing load balancing and response time. Such a process is called an object server. All processes wishing to operate on the object must send requests to the server through message passing. Processes that interact with the object in the form of requests are called clients of this object. If the object is critical for the operation of the entire distributed system, it is necessary to maintain several copies in the system, and these copies must be equivalent. Copies of an informational object are also called replicas. Two replicas of the same object are considered equivalent if the sets of bytes describing their states match completely. Through operations, the state of the object can change over time, and this can happen independently on each server in the absence of any synchronization. The interaction of processes during data replication is depicted in Figure 1.

Ideally, the same result is always obtained regardless of which replica the object server accesses. Therefore, the main goal is to achieve consistency among copies to ensure their continuous synchronization and provide consistent data. Maintaining consistency between different copies is particularly challenging when there are many copies or when they are located far from each other. In non-distributed systems, there are solutions to maintain absolute consistency, but they can negatively impact the overall system performance.

Data replication enhances system reliability, meaning that when one replica becomes unavailable, other replicas can continue processing requests. Replica unavailability can be caused by various factors, such as system failure, hardware failure of a node, or a network partition that prevents access to the node. Other reasons, such as scheduled maintenance or node reboot for software updates, can also make a replica unavailable. However, it is crucial to note that the exact details of how the replication system is implemented significantly impact system reliability. Without fault tolerance, having multiple replicas

can even make system reliability more critical, assuming failures are not correlated. The more replicas there are, the higher the likelihood that any one of them will fail at any given time.

Figure 2 illustrates a situation with two replicas, R1 and R2. Initially, both replicas initialize the key k with the value v_0 and timestamp t_0 . Then, a client attempts to update the key value to v_1 , with an associated timestamp t_1 . Replica R2 successfully updates, but replica R1 fails to update because it is temporarily unavailable. Later, the client tries to read the value it previously wrote. As a result, the read operation is successful on replica R1 but fails on replica R2. Subsequently, the new value v_1 , previously written by the same client, is not returned, but the initial value v_0 , is returned. This situation is undesirable because, from the client’s perspective, it appears that the last written value v_1 was lost.

There are various approaches to solving replication issues, which differ in the type of modification of the replicas. Let x be an informational object, P be the set of processes, $S \subseteq P$ be the set of servers where copies of object x are located, and $C \subseteq P$ be the set of clients of

object x . The corresponding sets of operational processes are denoted by a capital letter with the subscript op , for example, P_{op} is the set of operational processes.

The state machine replication method is based on the simultaneous modification of all copies of the object. The main issue with its application is the necessity to order client requests among all servers. The presence of a single order is a mandatory condition of this method. It is necessary to establish a linear order on the set of client requests M , in which these requests will be processed by the servers so that for any $\forall m_1, m_2 \in M, m_1 \neq m_2$, either $m_1 < m_2$ or $m_2 < m_1$ is true. Let $H_s \subseteq M$ be the set of requests received by server s and $H_{s,c} \subseteq H_s$ be the set of requests received by server s from client c . A request $m \in M$ is stable for server s if for all $\forall m' \in (M \setminus H_s)$, the inequality $m < m'$ is true. If all servers process only stable requests according to the given order, and each server receives every request, the order of processing requests will be the same for all servers.

To assign order to the set of client requests, a logical clock will be used. A logical clock is a mapping $T: e \rightarrow N$, which associates a natural number with each

Fig. 1. Interaction of replication processes

Fig. 2. Asynchronous replication Scenario

event in the system. For two different events e and e' , the condition $T^{\sim}(e) < T^{\sim}(e')$ or $T^{\sim}(e') < T^{\sim}(e)$ must be true. If the occurrence of event e' depends on event e , then the correct inequality is $T^{\sim}(e) < T^{\sim}(e')$.

To implement a logical clock in distributed systems, each process p is associated with a counter T^{\sim}_p . The value $T^{\sim}_p(m)$ is transmitted with all messages m sent by p . It is assumed that at any given time, each server knows the set of operational clients $C_{up} \subseteq C$.

When using a logical clock, a request m is considered stable for the servers if $\forall c \in C_{up} \exists m' \in H_{s,c} : T^{\sim}_c(m) < T^{\sim}_c(m')$. It should be noted that this method places the responsibility for replication on the clients. Clients must send their requests to all servers, and each client must periodically send heartbeat messages to all servers to ensure system progress.

In such conditions, data segmentation across multiple databases, where each database processes a subset of users, has the potential for successful implementation. This concept is known as sharding, which involves distributing data across multiple databases or machines.

Each segment (shard) functions as a replicated data system consisting of several processors. Thus, they collectively handle client requests and transactions by adhering to the classic consensus mechanism. These segments, operating as replicated data systems, can interact with other shards and jointly process transactions between them.

The task in a distributed system is defined as processing requests by processor nodes after achieving distributed consensus and then storing the result in the associated segment. A request is denoted as $Rv \in input = \{R1, R2, \dots\}$, representing the input set of the network sent from a set of clients denoted as $Cl = \{n_{c1}, n_{c2}, \dots, n_{ck}\}$, where each client is denoted by n_c . The set of processors is denoted as $P_r = \{n_{p1}, n_{p2}, \dots, n_{pv}\}$, and each processor is denoted by np .

Each processor is a member of a subset group in the network N , called a cluster and denoted as γ . The set of clusters is denoted by $\Gamma = \{\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \dots, \gamma_s\}$, where each cluster itself is a set of processors. Each cluster processes a subset of requests to share processing operations, aiming to improve the system's scalability, throughput, and performance.

Each shard is denoted by s_i , and the set of shards forms the entire system $N = \cup_{i=1}^S s_i$, where S represents the total number of shards in the system. After joining a cluster, each processor node sends a request to the current members to obtain the latest state of the shard's replicated data.

For each node N_k in the network, a maximum capacity C_k of storage devices is defined, which determines the maximum possible volume of data array replicas that can be placed in the node. Additionally, for each network node, a constraint AM_k is established on the maximum number of replicas of different data arrays that can be placed in this node k .

For arrays of data and their replicas, the capacity is defined as $Crd()$. The number of fixed-length records $Len(A_m)$, which equals the sum of the lengths of the record's attributes in the array. The volume (size) $AV(A_m)$ of the array F_m and its replicas is determined by the formula:

$$AV(A_m) = Crd(A_m) * Len(A_m) \tag{1}$$

$Len(A_m)$ is the fixed length of a record in array m :

$$Len(A_m) = \sum_{i=1}^{NA_m} LA_{im} \tag{2}$$

The NA_m – is the number of attributes in the record of array A_m and LA_{im} – is the length of the i -th attribute of the record in the array. Then the size (volume) of the replica and the array A_m itself is equal to:

$$AV(A_m) = Crd(A_m) * \sum_{i=1}^{NA_m} LA_{im} \tag{3}$$

Therefore, it is necessary to find such a distribution X of data array replicas across the nodes of a distributed system that ensures the minimum average response time to requests to data array replicas. The total volume of all replicas of arrays located in a single network node should not exceed the capacity of that:

$$\sum_{m=1}^M x_{mk} * Vol(A_m) \leq C_k, 1 \leq k \leq K \tag{4}$$

In each network node, the number of replicas placed should not exceed the specified maximum number of replicas AM_k for that particular node:

$$\sum_{m=1}^M x_{mk} \leq *AM_k, 1 \leq k \leq K \tag{5}$$

The original of each data array Am must be distributed in one of the network nodes:

$$\sum_{m=1}^M x_{mk} = 1, 1 \leq k \leq M \tag{6}$$

The distribution of data array replicas should ensure an average request processing time $AvRPT$ that does not exceed the maximum value $Tmax$:

$$AvRPT \leq Tmax \tag{7}$$

In the first stage of the algorithm, the elements of the priority matrix NP for the nodes are calculated. The value of the element $NP(N_k, A_m)$ of the matrix is equal to the sum of all requests to the array A_m generated in the node N_k per unit of time interval.

For all K nodes in the network and for each of the M data arrays, the value $NP(N_k, A_m)$ of the node priority is calculated.

Based on the elements of the NP matrix, the set of values NP_{range} is determined, which represents the range of values that the minimum priority constraint NP_{min} can take.

The next step involves calculating the range within which the value of the NP_{min} constraint will change in a loop, which is used to determine the possibility of placing replicas in the system nodes.

A replica of array m can be placed in node k if the node's priority $NP(N_k, A_m)$ is greater than or equal to the minimum value:

$$NP(N_k, A_m) \geq NP_{min} \tag{8}$$

To determine the range of possible values and the specific value of NP_{min} , the element NP_{max} with the maximum priority value and the element with the minimum priority value NP_{low} are sought among the elements of the NP matrix. Then, the step value for changing the constraint NP_{dlt} is calculated:

$$NP_{dlt} = (NP_{max} - NP_{min}) / Nc \tag{9}$$

where Nc represents the number of steps for changing the priority constraint of the nodes, and this number is determined when setting the task.

During replication, the most optimal distribution of replicas will be sought, and several variants of replica distribution Nc will be generated by successively using the constraint value NP_{min} from the NP_{range} set:

$$NP_{range} = \{NP_{low}, NP_{low} + NP_{dlt}, NP_{low} + 2NP_{dlt}, \dots, NP_{low} + (Nc - 1)NP_{dlt}\} \tag{10}$$

The next task in developing the data replication algorithm involves placing the originals of data arrays for their subsequent replication. Originals of all data arrays used in the system are placed across the network nodes. Each array m is placed in node k , which for this particular array has the highest node priority value $NP(N_k, A_m)$, that is, the original of the array is placed in the network node where the highest number of requests for this array is generated.

For testing the proposed algorithm, a distributed system with data arrays was simulated, containing records about the number of employees and vacant positions in various departments of an organization. Each record in the dataset is characterized by several key attributes: «Department» classifies employees based on their respective organizational units, such as marketing, human resources, finance, IT, etc., and the parameter «Number of employees» N_w .

Table 1. Data arrays

Data array	Department	Number of employees
1	Marketing	58
2	HR	24
3	Finance	36
4	IT	41

The testing of the algorithm was conducted using a distributed system operating within a computer network consisting of 10 nodes. The network topology is represented by a weighted graph $G=(K, \Gamma)$. The edges of the graph are colored with weights representing the average time dt_{ij} for transmitting messages (data units) between pairs of adjacent graph nodes $N_i, N_j (i, j = 1, K)$.

The distributed system under consideration has the following parameters: $K = 10$ – the number of nodes in the network, $P = 6$ – the number of application processes handling requests, which are executed in the network nodes and generate requests to the replicas of data arrays. $M = 4$ – the number of different data arrays, each of which can have multiple replicas placed in various network nodes.

Table 2 presents the values of the DTC matrix elements, which correspond to the average message transmission time between the nodes of the distributed system.

Table 2. Average data unit transmission time via the shortest paths between nodes of the distributed system

Node	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1	0	15	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	15	0	15	0	14	0	0	0	0	0
3	15	15	0	17	20	17	0	22	0	0
4	21	0	17	0	0	18	0	0	0	0
5	29	14	0	0	0	0	0	14	18	0
6	32	0	0	18	0	0	12	20	0	0
7	44	0	18	0	0	12	0	16	0	12
8	37	0	0	0	14	20	16	0	12	17
9	47	0	0	0	18	0	0	12	0	14
10	54	0	0	0	0	0	12	17	14	0

The adjusted cost matrix SPC is calculated by using the overall frequency as a factor. This metric is calculated for the number of workers in each department using the provided DTC matrix. The overall frequency factor helps to weight the transmission times based on the frequency of communication or data requests between the nodes, adjusting the costs accordingly to reflect the operational dynamics of the distributed system more accurately:

$$SPC(i, j) = DTC(i, j) * N_w \tag{11}$$

The SPC matrix of message transmission costs for a unit length via the shortest paths of the graph is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Cost of transmitting a message of unit length via the shortest path between nodes of the distributed system

Node	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1	0	360	360	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	360	0	360	0	336	0	0	0	0	0
3	360	360	0	408	20	408	0	528	0	0
4	504	0	408	0	0	432	0	0	0	0
5	696	336	0	0	0	0	0	336	432	0
6	768	0	0	432	0	0	288	480	0	0
7	1056	432	432	0	0	288	0	384	0	288
8	888	0	0	0	336	20	384	0	288	408
9	1134	0	0	0	432	0	0	288	0	336
10	1296	0	0	0	0	0	288	408	336	0

Subsequently, the migration of replicas to new network nodes is carried out if necessary according to the new distribution. In the process of migrating each data array $m = 1, \dots, M$ according to the new distribution, the node or nodes k in the network where the replica of array m should be placed ($x_{mk} = 1$) are identified. Then, a node n in the network $n = 1, \dots, K$ is searched for, where according to the previous distribution, the replica of array $m (x_{nm} = 1)$ is stored. There can be multiple such nodes in the network since multiple replicas of one array can be placed in different network nodes. From these nodes with the replica, the node n that is located at the shortest distance from node k is selected. After that, the replica of array m from node n is copied (migrated) to node k .

CONCLUSION

Overall, data replication across multiple nodes within a distributed system, organizations can reduce the risks

associated with single points of failure and enhance the overall performance of the system. Using a dataset that contains detailed records about employees and testing the proposed replication algorithm on this dataset provided insights into the effectiveness of replication strategies in real scenarios.

The testing process demonstrated the algorithm's ability to efficiently distribute and synchronize data, thereby increasing data access speed, reducing latency, and ensuring consistency among distributed nodes. Additionally, the results of the testing process highlight the

importance of choosing appropriate replication mechanisms based on specific requirements and constraints of the distributed database environment. Factors such as data consistency, network latency, resource usage, and fault tolerance must be carefully considered when developing and implementing replication strategies. Finally, it is essential to note that integrating data replication methods into distributed databases allows organizations to meet the increasing demands for data availability, reliability, and performance in today's dynamic business landscape.

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